

International Conference on **ICGB 2017** Green Banking Perceptions and Challenges

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(A Constituent College of Mangalore University)
Accredited with 'A' Grade by NAAC

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Excel
INDIA PUBLISHERS

EXCEL INDIA PUBLISHERS
NEW DELHI

First Impression: February, 2017

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International Conference on Green Banking: Perceptions and Challenges

ISBN: 978-93-86256-39-3

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Published by

EXCEL INDIA PUBLISHERS

91 A, Ground Floor

Pratik Market, Munirka, New Delhi-110067

Tel: +91-11-2671 1755/ 2755/ 3755/ 5755

Fax: +91-11-2671 6755

E-mail: publishing@groupexcelindia.com

Web: www.groupexcelindia.com

Typeset by

Excel Publishing Services, New Delhi-110067

E-mail: prepress@groupexcelindia.com

Printed by

Excel Printing Universe, New Delhi-110067

E-mail: printing@groupexcelindia.com

Green Banking Initiatives in Uttara Kannda District

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Abstract—Bank plays a significant role in the development of the country. Green Banking is a form of normal bank which involves ethical consideration that is social and environmental factors its main objective is to safeguard and conserve our natural resource by reducing carbon footprints. The research methodology used in this study is based on both primary as well as secondary data from selected commercial Banks In Uttara Kannada District. Finally the concept of green banking is beneficiary for not only banking sector alone but also to the companies, industries and whole economy. It is a path towards implementing quality of banking activities

Keywords: Initiative, Products, Commercial Bank, Save Paper, EFT

INTRODUCTION

Bank plays a significant role in the development of the country. It is a main source of finance which invests money in various sectors to achieve economic growth of the country considering ethical factors, so bank had taken a concept of green banking as its main strategy. It results in healthy environmental condition and which gives more importance to the ecological factors. Green banking plays a pivotal role in protecting environment with the aim of creating good social activities. It is a technique of reducing of carbon emissions and improves financial assistance to green technology and making pollution free environment. It is a way of accelerating the growth and development of the economy by influencing on the financial world. It reduces the paperwork by introducing ecofriendly system that is usage of electronic media instead of paper transaction. Green banking plays a prominent role in the protection of natural resources.

MEANING OF GREEN BANKING

Green Banking is a form of normal bank which involves ethical consideration that is social and environmental factors its main objective is to safeguard and conserve our natural resource by reducing carbon footprints. Green banking gives more weightage to the environmental factors which enhances good business practice. It involves online bill payments, using online banking, ATM, Green credit card etc.

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

- To study the green banking concept.
- To study the various products involved in green banking
- To study the green banking initiatives in Uttara kannada District.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is conducted based on primary and secondary data. These data are collected from different commercial bank in Uttara Kannada District. The Banks are selected on the basis of random sampling. In addition to this, the data is also collected through annual report, daily news paper, different journals, articles and bank's websites.

GREEN BANKING PRODUCTS IN UTTARA KANNADA DISTRICT

There are several products involved in green banking. They are as follows

MOBILE BANKING

It is a facility given by bank to its customers for carrying out the financial transactions through mobile phones. It is new technique and more popularizing today. A customer can make payment like electronic payments, transferring funds and enable to check balance, stop cheque payments, get accounting information etc through mobile banking. So the apps in mobile phones helps to copy or download the electronic statements and thereby reduce the quantity of papers. It saves time, efforts and energy of prospective customer. In U.K. district this product is used by young youths in more number. So 75% of people using this and remaining 25% of people are not using these products.

NET BANKING

Nowadays, E-commerce and internet is gradually growing. World Wide Web is converting entire world in to digital world. It offers new techniques of dealing with banking practice. It allows the user that he can access through banking website and avail any of the banking sources and functions. It improves banking relationship and encourage customers and reduces transaction cost at all. It helps the customer to perform the easily without visiting banks and it ignores late payment and payment of bill from home online. This product also used by youths mainly in these days and those who have good knowledge of using electronic media. However 75% of them are using this product and rest 25% are not using.

ATM

ATM stands for AUTOMATED TELLER MACHINE. It provides any time money. A customer can withdraw the amount through ATM without visiting to the bank branches. It provides 24*7 service. One can withdraw the amount in any time. This facility is available only in urban areas. So in U.K district urban area people get this opportunity and rural people may not get because of non-availability of ATM in rural area.

GREEN CREDIT CARD

It's a plastic card, which helps the card holder to purchase goods without making payments immediately. The borrowed amount is like a loan amount and interest is charged for that

amount. The main rules followed here is "Buy now, pay later". Bank provides funds to the eco friendly organizations from every rupee is spent on credit card and it provides a reasonable impact on protection of environment. In U.K district this credit card is not so popularized. It is used 55% rarely by the people.

PAPERLESS TRANSACTION OR SAVE PAPER

Computers are popularly used by the banking sector through reduces the paper transactions. Mainly public sector undertakings use more quantity of paper in preparing reports, recordings, statements etc. Banks should accelerate their customer to switch over to the electronic transaction and thereby popularizes e-statements. Banks allows the customers to get electronic statements with the help of secure log-in. It creates good business practices.

Banks also use recycled paper products in order to prepare annual reports, ATM reports, envelops and monthly statements. Here mainly vegetable based ink is used to protect the nature. SBI is mainly using this product. In U.K district 2-3 banks are using save paper only 30% are using this product.

ONLINE BILL PAYMENT

Now a days paying the bills through online is becoming new trend. One can pay telephone bills, credit card payments, mortgage payments, and utility bills electronically. It saves the time and efforts of the people standing in line for payments. In U.K district 25% people are using and rest 75% are not go with online bill payment may be due to lack of knowledge of this product.

ONLINE SAVING ACCOUNT

Online saving account is the easiest way to the green banking system. Green Banking implies in setting up direct deposits to receive e-statements, pay checks from bank and it reduces the paper work. Green banking also facilitates "Remote Deposits" which permits banks to clear the checks digitally. It is not popularized in U.K district only 10% to 15% of users are using.

SMS ALERTS

Now a days, mobile phones are used highly and it is the fastest channels of communication. Banks offers a special service called SMS alerts to stay updated on accounting transaction through mobile. So to avail this service customer has to register for the service he need to be fill registration form(PNB1167) and submit the same to the bank. On successful registration customer will receive confirmation SMS. Customer can receive SMS alerts for the withdrawal through ATM and large payment through credit card etc. SMS alerts are popularized in U.K district, 80% of customers get this alerts.

EFT

It stands for Electronic Fund Transfer. It is based on internet in which funds are transferred from one place to another and from one account to another account using electronic media. All physical forms of financial papers like cheques, drafts, etc are converted in to electronic forms and that amount debited or credited to the customers account based on his request. So, every transactions easily done by using computers. EFT is popularized in U.K. district 70% of the customers get this service.

SOLAR ENERGY

Installation of solar power in India indicates the fastest growth. India ranked number one in solar electricity production. Banks adopted green energy to improve solar system to power their branches. Solar energy is installed by the banks to meet daily requirements of electricity. Banks faced with problem such as regular power cuts. Due to this tube lights, fans, computers, servers are not operating as per their need during load shedding hours. This system offers a continuous electricity cost and neglects the usage of diesel generator which emits carbon. It ensures a long life for the battery and better quality of power. Solar system provides clean energy and it is more economical. solar energy used by the banks in U.K. district.

GREEN BANKING INITIATIVES IN U.K. DISTRICT

Green banking initiatives undertaken by both private and public sector banks. They are:

STATE BANK OF INDIA [SBI]

- SBI termed as the first bank adopted green practice by installing windmills.
- SBI had introduced Green Channel Counter at their branches to minimize paper based banking in 2010.
- To provide long terms loans up to 14 years SBI and EXIM bank entered into agreement with Spain based company Astonfied Renewable Resource and Grupo T-solor Global SA for building solar plant in India.
- SBI launched new scheme called green homes that facilitates softer interest rate, reduce margin and zero processing fees on home loans for environmental friendly activities.
- There are more than 17 SBI branches in U.K. district they are as follows: Ankola, Bhatkal, Chittakala, Dandeli, Haliyal, Honnavar, Karwar, Karwar port complex, Kumta, Malgi, Naval Base Karwar, NPCC Kaiga, Shivaji chowk Sirsi, Siddapur, Sirsi, Tadri, Yellapur, all these branches adopted green practice and reduces the paper transaction.

CANARA BANK

- Canara bank had taken green banking strategy in 2013.
- Bank had set up ecofriendly measures as technique of green banking such as telebanking, SMS banking, mobile banking, solar powered biometric operation etc thereby decreases the quantity of paper work.
- Bank claims initiatives to improve e-governance for HRM functions and ensuring a reduction of paper transaction in many areas.
- Canara bank gives more preference to high-tech banking facilities like net banking, online trading, telebanking, passbook printing kiosk, ATM etc.
- In the way of lending policy they provide aggregate preference to the solar energy and windmills projects.
- There are 25 canara bank branches in U.K district such as Ankola, BK Halli, Balkur, Bandala, Bhagavathi, Castle Rock, Chandavar, Dandeli, Halge, Haliyal, Heggare, Honnavar, Hosagadde, Hubli road Sirsi, Janmane, Karwar, Kumta, Mugwa, Mundagod, Nandangada, Pala, Siddapur, Sirsi, Thungani, Venkatapur.

ICICI BANK LTD

- ICICI Bank had taken “Go Green “ technique interms of green product, green communication, green partners etc with its customer 2014:
- Green product or services:

ICICI bank provides green product and services such as:

1. **Vehicle Finance:** It provides 50% of waiver on processing fee of auto loans on the car models.
2. **Home Finance:** Customers who are buying home in LEED certified buildings, the bank had decreased processing fees.
3. **Insta Banking:** Which allows customers to carryout banking activities anywhere through mobile banking, net banking in any time.
 - Green communication

Bank assist their prospective customers for EFT, Online bill payment, Green credit card etc to minimize paper transaction and implementing electronic transactions.

- Green partners

The organization started partnership with national and international green organization and NGO's to safeguard environment and it ensures pollution free environment.

- There are 6 ICICI bank branches in U.K district they protects our nature by reducing carbon emissions. They are as follows; Bhatkal, Dandeli, Karwar, Kumta, Sirsi, Yellapur.

HDFC BANK LTD

- HDFC bank had including green banking strategy as its initiative in its activities to make reduction of carbon footprints and to use solar power as per HDFC Bank 2013:
- Its special initiative is to minimize the wasteful usage of natural resources totally.
- Banks are frequently decreasing the paper quantity by improving electronic transactions and they are communicating with their potential customers through electronic media which ensures improvement of e-transactions.
- Banks playing a crucial role in the usage of CFL conventional lighting. After 11 PM switch offs all the lights at all branches and set ups green data centers thereby popularizing energy efficiencies.
- They are often contact with vendors for recycling of their waste paper and plastic thereby gives protection to our nature.
- It encourages to the green banking products and services.
- HDFC Banks set up the system of sending identification number i.e. pin number to the debit card holders through SMS.
- There are 4 HDFC bank branches at U.K. district. They are as follows: Honnavar, Karwar, Kumta, Sirsi.

AXIS BANK LTD

- Axis Bank also included green banking strategies as per Axis Bank 2013:
- The bank had undertaken recycling process in August 2011 by assembling all waste papers and plastics from its corporate office and its branches and thereby producing notebooks, envelopes, note pads till now more than 1,00,000 kg's of paper has been recycled. It ensures healthy environmental status.
- The corporate office of the bank, Mumbai implementing platinum LEED certified "Green Building".
- They motivate their customers to use electronic media for communication and e-statements to decrease the usage of quantity of paper.
- Banks are promoting Independent ATM Deployment (IAD) model which is ten solar based.

- All documents, annual reports, statements of banks are sent through emails.
- There are 4 axis bank branches in U.K. districts as follows: Bhatkal, Karwar, Kumta, Sirsi.

KOTAK MAHINDRA BANK

The bank had taken 'Think Green' steps as per Kotak Mahindra Bank 2013:

- Bank insisting their customers to go with e-transaction.
- They have become partners with "Grow Trees.com" to plant one sapling for every e-statement on behalf of their prospective customers.
- According to the guidelines set by Ministry of Corporate Affairs (MCA), banks prominently improved electronic copies of annual reports by replacing paper copies.
- In order to prevent pollution it has been installed rain water harvesting tank and makes pollution free environment.
- Banks playing a significant role In the usage of solar energy and E-transaction to reduce carbon foot prints.
- There are two bank branches in U.K district. They are at Karwar and Sirsi.

CONCLUSION

Banks are the main source of finance. It plays an important role in the economic development. Banks are using huge quantity of papers to prepare reports, statements which emits carbon it cause pollution. Pollution harm the health and wealth of the economy. To remove these obstacle banks under taken several initiative green banking strategy to work towards global environment. In this way, Indian banking sector implemented several sustainable projects that could accelerate innovative product or services in the area of green banking. It reduces the paper work and encourages to the e-transaction. It contributes a lot to the environment. So this techniques adopted by banks of U.K Districts banks which enables fast work and conserves time and efforts and also makes healthy environment condition by minimizing carbon emissions. so another banks also including this green steps.

RBI and Indian Government should play a pro-active role in formulating green policy and practices. However, green strategy brings more awareness about global warming and it is good way of development.

So, finally the concept of green banking is beneficiary for not only banking sector alone but also to the companies, industries and whole economy. it is a path towards implementing quality of banking activities.

REFERENCES

- [1] Garg, Shruti (2015), "Green Banking: An Overview", *Global Journal of Advanced Research*, Vol. 2, Issue 8, August, pp. 1291–1296.
- [2] George, Ajimon (2013), "A Customer Centric Study on Internet Banking in Kerala", Mahatma Gandhi University Kottayam, March.
- [3] Raghupathi, M. and Sujatha, S. (2015), "Green Banking Initiatives of Commercial Banks in India", *International Research Journal of Business and Management*, Vol. 8, January, pp. 74–81.
- [4] Mahesh, A.C., Nirosha, M. and Pavithra, V. (2016), "Recent Trends in Indian Banking-Green Banking Initiative in India", *International Journal of Science Technology and Management*, Vol. 5, February, pp. 369–374.
- [5] Meena Ravi (2013), "Green Banking: As Initiative for Sustainable Development", *Global Journal of Management of Business Studies*, Vol. 3, November, pp. 1181–1186.
- [6] www.axisbank.com
- [7] www.canarabank.in
- [8] www.hdfcbank.com
- [9] www.icicibank.com
- [10] www.kotak.com
- [11] www.onlinesbi.com
- [12] www.shodhganga.com
- [13] www.wikipedia.com